

ISic1389

Greek funerary inscription of Kallistratos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

Described by Gualtherus (1624) as coming from the ruins popularly identified with the shrine of the god Hadranus (not identified). All later editions derive from Gualtherus.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

The stone is one of three described as 'petra nigra' by Gualtherus (1624: 50), but neither state of conservation nor dimensions are recorded.

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

The text is presented as split over three lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain transcription in standard capitals makes it impossible to assess the letter-forms.

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Καλλίς

2. τρατος

3. 'Ράτορος

Apparatus

Text after Gualtherus and later editors

Gualtherus: KAMΙΣ (followed by Torremuzza)

Translation (en)

Kallistratos, son of Rhator

Commentary

The stone is presented in the edition of Gualtherus (1624, p.50 nr. 337) under the same heading as ISic1386 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1386>], and so the same report appears to apply, namely 'petra nigra', state of conservation and dimensions not recorded; it is said to have come from the ruins popularly equated with the site of the temple of the local divinity Adranos. It is not clear why Kaibel (IG XIV, 570) says 'admodum recens reperta', i.e. only recently recovered. The name Καμιστρατος recorded by Gualtherus is not attested, and the emendation of M to ΛΛ proposed by Franz, reflecting a misreading of the original, is straightforward. Καλλίστρατος [http://clas-lgpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%9A%CE%B1%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%AF%CF%83%CF%84%CF%81%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%82] is common, with a couple of other attestations from Sicily. The name Πάτωρ is not otherwise attested; however, a name with an indigenous origin is possible, as a couple of possibly cognate forms are attested: Πατορώ [http://clas-lgpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BF%AC%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%81%CF%8E] on a lead tablet, possibly from Terravecchia di Cuti, although the reading is far from certain (Arena, *Iscrizioni*, II, no.117A / Dubois, *IGDS I*, no.176 a); and Πατορᾶς [http://clas-lgpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BF%AC%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%81%E1%BE%B6%CF%82] on a vase inscription from Montagna di Marzo (Herbessos?) (Kokalos 14-15 (1968-9) p. 200). Earlier editors speculated that this might not be a name but the title of rhetor, and Osann (1834, p. 98 n. 1) offered several alternative readings and identifications, and in particular made the very tenuous suggestion that this might be the Attic rhetor Kallistratos, buried in Sicily after being condemned by the Athenians. Franz in *CIG* 3.5739 was politely dismissive (rightly).

It is impossible to date this text, in the absence of further information, although it is most likely to belong to the Hellenistic period.

Digital identifiers:

TM 493004

EDR 149504

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Bibliography

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